

Research plan/Protocol for HRO:

Further use of biological material and health-related personal data for research **without consent pursuant to Article 34 HRA**

Title of the research project

Maternal and Neonatal outcomes in Association with midwifery Staffing (MaNTiS) – A causal inference framework

Name and address of the project leader

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Confirmation of the project leader

With my signature, I attest that all information in this protocol is correct and that I will comply with the information I have given and with national legislation, namely data protection law.

Project leader: Prof Dr Michael Simon

Basel, 13.02.2024

Place, date

Signature

Abbreviations

CHOP	Swiss classification of procedures
CDW	Clinical Data Warehouse
DAG	Directed acyclic graph
DRG	Diagnosis-Related Group
EHR	Electronic Health Record
HRA	Human Research Act
HRO	Human Research Ordinance
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
INS	Institute of Nursing Science
LOS	Length of stay
MaNtiS	Maternal and Neonatal outcomes in Association with midwifery Staffing
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
NICU	Neonatal Intensive Care Unit
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
RM	Registered Midwife
RN	Registered Nurse
SNSF	Swiss National Science Foundation
SPHN	Swiss Personalised Health Network
USB	University Hospital Basel

1. Background

In Switzerland 98% of children are born in hospitals (1). Considering that we will face a midwifery staffing shortage in Swiss hospitals in the next five years (2), research on the impact of staffing on maternal and neonatal outcomes is essential to match demand and supply (3). Current reports on maternity care staffing in the literature are highly heterogeneous, with different ratios such as midwife-to-women, proportion of one-to-one care or hours of care per delivery (4–7). Furthermore, most studies also aggregate these ratios in place and time, e.g., on hospital level (5) and on yearly birth numbers (8). This gives a high degree of uncertainty on staffing variation itself, its association with outcomes and at which point staffing reaches a critical threshold.

Maternal and neonatal outcomes

The salutogenic paradigm is a concept of health promotion and in childbirth, to foster a natural physiologic intervention-free vaginal birth. This is in contrast to today's health care delivery, where the focus is on risk minimisation and therefore often intervening in maternity care (9). This has led to over treatment, such as high labour induction rates, caesarean sections or medically accelerated births (9,10). Any type of over treatment should be reduced while maintaining patient safety. To counteract the development toward over treatment, the World Health Organisation published recommendations in the field of intrapartum care for a positive childbirth experience, where this health-promoting paradigm of salutogenesis is applied (11,12). A central part of implementing these recommendations is the provision of adequate staffing levels in maternity care (one-to-one care), which enable to follow a salutogenic paradigm.

Throughout the research project, we follow the definition of normal physiologic childbirth from the American College of Nurse-Midwives, the Midwives Alliance of North America and the National Association of Certified Professional Midwives who published a consensus statement (13). Normal physiologic childbirth is marked by spontaneous onset and progression of labour; ends in a spontaneous vaginal birth of the infant and placenta with physiological blood loss. Furthermore, physiologic childbirth enhances the optimal newborn transition through early skin-to-skin contact and initiation of breastfeeding (13).

Causal inference in physiological childbirth

To better understand how staffing influences maternity care, it must be linked to measurable maternal and neonatal outcomes. The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guideline particularly pointed out that there is a lack of research in the maternity setting (3). Especially the lack of studies aiming to establish a causal link between staffing and outcomes have led possible solutions for the improvement of maternity care to remain elusive (14). In childbirth randomized controlled trials are generally difficult to conduct due to both organisational and ethical reasons. Therefore, we need methodology to infer causes and effect relationships from observational data (15). To address such causal questions, the causal inference provides a suitable framework. A series of three articles discussing the causal inference framework to study physiological childbirth has provided a practical basis for its application (15–17).

Staffing and Outcomes

Midwifery staffing levels based on demand and supply were assessed and described in a previous study conducted in the same clinical site, as this study is targeted [Req-2022-00208, EKNZ]. The care demand of birthing parents could be addressed in around 70% of shifts in the labour ward. In the remaining 30% of shifts, one-to-one care could not be provided to all women, because they were short of at least one midwife (18).

A scoping review, including 23 studies, on the association of midwifery and nurse staffing of maternity services and outcomes has highlighted this relationship (19). Due to the cross-sectional designs and aggregations on hospital level a causal link of staffing and outcomes yet remains difficult to determine (19). The review included few salutogenic outcomes, such as the rate of births with an intact perineum, with a higher odds ratio (OR) of 1.13 (95% CI 1.01-1.27) compared to lower staffing (10). Again, comparing midwifery staffing levels, exclusive breastfeeding was found in 88% of birth giving parents in a setting with higher staffing levels compared to 78% in a setting with lower staffing levels (6), resulting in an OR of 2.04 (95% CI 1.07-3.92). Furthermore, better adherence to staffing recommendations for the labour ward have a positive effect on exclusive breast milk feeding (Lyndon et al., 2022). In the postpartum period higher staffing levels showed an association with birth giving parents reporting more often that staff always helped in a reasonable time (aOR 1.2, 95% CI 1.04-1.27) (20).

The purpose of this research project is to inform clinical practice with evidence about the effects of staffing on the birth giving parents and newborns. With this knowledge health outcomes can be improved by promoting physiologic processes while improving midwifery staffing in hospital settings.

2. Objectives

This research project aims to investigate the causal effect of midwifery staffing levels on maternal and neonatal salutogenic outcomes (physiological vaginal birth; labour pain; exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge; healthy newborn; length of stay).

Primary Objective:

Investigate the causal effect of midwifery staffing levels on the prevalence of physiological vaginal births.

Secondary Objectives:

Investigate the causal effect of midwifery staffing levels on labour pain; exclusive breastfeeding; healthy newborn and length of stay.

The assessed outcomes are defined as follows:

Outcome 1: Physiological vaginal birth – vaginal birth without labour-accelerating interventions, including oxytocin administration, artificial rupture of membranes, episiotomy and all instrumental births.

Outcome 2: Labour pain – Non-use of pharmacological pain treatment during labour with a high degree of intervention, including epidural analgesia, personal controlled analgesia with remifentanyl, nalbuphine and nitrous oxide.

Outcome 3: Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge – no supplementary feeding during the previous 24 hours.

Outcome 4: Healthy newborn – is a composite measure of temperature, glucose levels, physiological jaundice and 24h rooming-in.

Outcome 5: Length of stay (LOS) – birth giving parent and newborn separately.

3. Design

The MaNTiS project is a retrospective observational study using longitudinal routine data. The midwifery staffing levels will be used from the previous study [Req-2022-00208, EKNZ] (18). The outcome data will be use of further health-related data of inpatients from the maternity department of the University Hospital Basel (USB) over the time frame between 01. Jan 2019 and 31. Dec 2022.

To identify relevant variables as confounders and reduce the number of necessary variables to be extracted to a minimum we worked with causal inference tools (directed acyclic graphs, DAGs). In causal inference, not only the outcomes are relevant but also all confounding factors that could influence the causal effect from staffing levels on the outcomes. Therefore, we need data on the outcomes and all factors that might have an influence.

Due to the high variation in care demand, the causal effect of staffing on demand is dependent on this variation. Therefore, we aim to analyse a four-year period, which then entails around 10,000 births. This results in approximately 10,000 mothers and 10,000 newborns that will be assessed, in total 20,000 individuals.

There will be different data sets that will be used: 1) Administrative patient data and 2) Clinical patient data from the electronic health record (EHR). The data is stored in the clinical data warehouse (CDW) of the USB and all variables are described further in chapter eight.

The causal effect of midwifery staffing on maternal and neonatal salutogenic outcomes will be derived using suitable causal inference methods (such as marginal structure models, inverse-probability-of-treatment weighted estimators, g-methods) (21).

To assess the risk for health-related data de-identification the methodology of Swiss Personalised Health Network (SPHN) was applied. The total risk score is 0.5, which corresponds to a low risk. The accompanying excel sheet is uploaded as further document.

4. Origin of the data/biological material

This health-related data will be extracted from all births that meet the inclusion criteria. For each birth, there is a birth giving parent and at least one newborn. The vast majority of the data that we plan to use come from administrative patient data, which is obtained in order to report to the Swiss Federal Statistical Office due to the obligation to report the medical statistics of hospitals (22).

Further data we need will be extracted from the EHR system Meona, from which medication use, newborn feeding, and newborn temperature, glucose levels and bilirubin levels can be extracted (23).

5. Inclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria are different for each outcome:

Outcome 1: Physiological vaginal birth

- 1) Person that has a spontaneous vaginal birth ($n \approx 5,000$)
- 2) Age equal or older than 18 years
- 3) Birth took place in the labour ward

Outcome 2: Labour pain

- 1) Person that has experienced labour ending in vaginal birth (n ≈ 5,000)
- 2) Age equal or older than 18 years
- 3) Birth took place in the labour ward

Outcome 3: Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge

- 1) Person that has given birth in the labour ward, who is willing to breastfeed (n ≈ 9,000)
- 2) Age equal or older than 18 years for person that has given birth
- 3) Newborn hospitalised on postnatal unit (n ≈ 9,000)
- 4) Discharged from hospital to home

Outcome 4: Healthy newborn

- 1) Newborn hospitalised on postnatal unit (n ≈ 9,000)
- 2) Discharged from hospital to home

Outcome 5: Length of stay (LOS)

- 1) Person that has given birth in the labour ward
- 2) Newborn that was born in the labour ward

6. Exclusion criteria

For all outcomes, the documented refusal of general consent is an exclusion criterion.

For all outcomes, maternal and neonatal perinatal deaths are excluded.

All newborns that are transferred to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) are excluded.

7. Scientific methods and sample size

The causal effect of midwifery staffing on maternal and neonatal salutogenic outcomes will be derived using suitable causal inference methods (such as marginal structure models, inverse-probability-of-treatment weighted estimators, g-methods) (21). For the different types of outcomes, appropriate models will be introduced (e.g., logistic regression or Cox regression). In the analysis we will account for clustering (e.g., by means of random effects) as appropriate and for the time component.

The data cleaning includes checks of the distribution, missing data, outliers and verification of merging procedures. For the descriptive analysis we will calculate medians, means, percentages, quartiles and standard deviations as appropriate. The analyses will be conducted using R on Linux with the packages like tidyverse, and padr (24–26).

Sample size

We expect a sample size of around 10'000 births. The potential strength of the association between midwifery staffing and salutogenic maternal and neonatal outcomes is unknown. Due to the high variation and clustering of number of births over a short period of time, we argue that a longer time frame could be necessary to fully understand the causal relationship.

Furthermore, the Covid-19 pandemic could be seen as a natural experiment of midwifery staffing levels. The pandemic hit in spring 2020 and with the selected time frame, we have data from one-year pre-covid, covid and counting 2023 as one-year post-covid. The covid time (2021 and 2022) period could be seen as some sort of staffing intervention, because we assume that staffing was reduced during this time due to illness of staff. This could be compared to “normal” levels of staffing (2019 and 2023).

Reproducibility and transparency

All the codes, but also text documents, protocols, etc created during the project will be versioned and saved on the INS server. For R code version control with git will be used. This will allow the research team to keep track of all modifications performed to those documents during the life of the project. To increase security (of losing codes), git will be linked to GitHub (<https://github.com/>) as a web-based repository. This will provide transparency within the research team, but also increase the reproducibility and decrease errors.

Bias

There are potential risks for bias. One possible bias is of course patients explicitly declining general consent. It is difficult to judge the effect on the final results, as it is not known if the patients who did decline the general consent have a different profile to those with a general consent. Another bias is the possibility of missing data in the EHR from omitted documentation and missing diagnoses in the discharge report. This leads to missing ICD codes, missing procedure codes and could result in a misclassification of cases (underestimation of interventions). Though, we expect the risk of missing diagnoses to be rather minor because special medical controllers are coding the cases. The risk of missing documentation is difficult to estimate, although information that is highly relevant for care, i.e. parity, pregnancy week and newborn surveillance measure is expected to be documented more rigorously.

8. For which health-related personal data/biological material should the authorization be granted?

We request authorization for routinely collected data for all patients who were hospitalized on the labour ward and postnatal unit between 2019 and 2022. All patients meeting our inclusion criteria, except those who have explicitly declined consent are included. The majority of data used is included in the medical statistics of hospitals from the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (22). The general consent was introduced at the USB before 2019, therefore, for all women that signed the consent, we do have written consent. The consent for the mother does not include consent for the newborn. In the data, it is possible to connect mother and newborn cases, but identifying all addresses from parents to ask for consent would overburden the PhD study. The remaining mothers without consent information would lead to a disproportionate workload to obtain consent. In Table 1, we have listed an approximate number of consents obtained and consents not available.

The operationalisation of each outcome is presented in Table 2 and the description of variables then follows in Table 3.

Table 1: Estimation of consents

	total number of data/ samples	number of data/ samples with consent	number without consent – person deceased	number without consent – person not contactable	total number of data/ samples without consent
USB Mothers	~10,000	~5,000 ~1,000 denied	-	~4,000	~4,000
USB Newborns	~10,000	0	-	~10,000	~10,000
USB	~20,000	~5,000	-	~14,000	~14,000

Table 2: Operationalisation of outcomes

Outcome & definition	Target population	Operationalisation	Variables	Measurement	Source of data
<p>Outcome 1 – Physiological vaginal birth</p> <p>Vaginal birth without labour-accelerating interventions.</p>	Mother	<p>Binary – yes/no</p> <p>Yes = NO interventions</p> <p>No = Labour-accelerating interventions</p>	<p>Labour-accelerating interventions:</p> <p>a) Syntocinon</p> <p>b) Artificial rupture of membranes</p> <p>c) Episiotomy</p> <p>d) Instrumental birth</p> <p>Confounders:</p> <p>e) Pregnancy week</p> <p>f) Age</p> <p>Inclusion / exclusion criteria:</p> <p>g) Mode of birth</p>	<p>Labour-accelerating interventions:</p> <p>a) Meona medication list</p> <p>b) CHOP code</p> <p>c) CHOP code</p> <p>d) CHOP code</p> <p>Confounders:</p> <p>e) ICD code</p> <p>f) Age in years</p> <p>Inclusion / exclusion criteria:</p> <p>g) ICD code + CHOP code</p>	<p>a) EHR</p> <p>b-g) Administrative patient data</p>

Outcome & definition	Target population	Operationalisation	Variables	Measurement	Source of data
<p>Outcome 2 – Labour pain</p> <p>Non-use of pharmacological pain treatment with a high degree of intervention during labour.</p>	Mother	<p>Binary – yes/no</p> <p>Yes = NO pharmacological interventions</p> <p>No = Pharmacological interventions</p>	<p>Pharmacological interventions:</p> <p>a) Epidural analgesia b) Spinal analgesia c) Personal controlled analgesia d) Nalbuphine administration e) Nitrous oxide administration</p> <p>Confounders:</p> <p>f) Gestational age g) Hypertension h) Age i) Induction of labour j) Nationality k) Adiposity</p> <p>Inclusion / exclusion criteria: l) Mode of birth</p>	<p>Pharmacological interventions:</p> <p>a) CHOP code b) CHOP code c) CHOP code d) Meona medication list e) Meona medication list</p> <p>Confounders:</p> <p>f) ICD code g) ICD code h) Age in years i) CHOP code j) Nationality k) ICD code</p> <p>Inclusion / exclusion criteria: ICD code + CHOP code</p>	<p>a-c) Administrative patient data</p> <p>d-e) EHR</p> <p>f)-l) Administrative patient data</p>

Outcome & definition	Target population	Operationalisation	Variables	Measurement	Source of data
<p>Outcome 3 – Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge</p> <p>Exclusive breastfeeding for the previous 24h before hospital discharge</p>	Mother Newborn	<p>Binary – yes/no</p> <p>Yes = Exclusive breastfeeding during previous 24 hours</p> <p>No = Supplementary feeding during the previous 24 hours before discharge</p>	<p>Newborn feeding:</p> <p>a) Supplementary feeding</p> <p>Confounders:</p> <p>b) Pregnancy week</p> <p>c) Congenital malformations</p> <p>d) Birth weight</p> <p>e) Mode of birth</p> <p>f) Maternal blood loss</p> <p>Inclusion / exclusion criteria:</p> <p>g) Able and willingness to breastfeed</p>	<p>Newborn feeding:</p> <p>a) Meona feeding list [newborn]</p> <p>Confounders:</p> <p>b) ICD code [mother]</p> <p>c) ICD code [newborn]</p> <p>d) Birth weight [newborn]</p> <p>e) ICD code + CHOP code [mother]</p> <p>f) Meona</p> <p>Inclusion / exclusion criteria:</p> <p>g) ICD code</p>	<p>a) EHR [newborn]</p> <p>b-e) Administrative patient data [mother & newborn]</p> <p>f) EHR [mother]</p> <p>g) administrative patient data [mother]</p>
<p>Outcome 4 – Healthy newborn</p> <p>Composite measure of physiological temperature values, glucose levels, jaundice and 24h rooming-in.</p>	Newborn	<p>Binary – yes/no</p> <p>Yes = Healthy newborn</p> <p>No = Complications during hospital stay (temperature, glucose, jaundice, admission to NICU)</p>	<p>Healthy newborn:</p> <p>a) Temperature</p> <p>b) Glucose levels</p> <p>c) Bilirubin levels</p> <p>d) Admission to NICU</p> <p>Confounders:</p> <p>e) Pregnancy week</p> <p>f) Age in days</p> <p>g) Birth weight</p> <p>h) Mode of birth</p> <p>i) Gestational diabetes</p> <p>j) Parity</p>	<p>Healthy newborn:</p> <p>a) Meona monitoring curve</p> <p>b) Meona monitoring curve</p> <p>c) Meona monitoring curve</p> <p>d) DRG code</p> <p>Confounders:</p> <p>e) ICD code / Meona</p> <p>f) Birth date</p> <p>g) Birth weight</p> <p>h) ICD code + CHOP code</p> <p>i) ICD code</p> <p>j) Meona</p>	<p>a-c) EHR</p> <p>d-i) Administrative patient data [newborn & mother]</p> <p>j) EHR</p> <p>k) Administrative patient data [newborn]</p>

Outcome & definition	Target population	Operationalisation	Variables	Measurement	Source of data
			Inclusion / exclusion criteria: k) Discharged home or to NICU	Inclusion / exclusion criteria: k) Place of discharge	
Outcome 5 – Length of stay (LOS) Normal duration of LOS based on DRG definitions.	Mother Newborn	Binary – Normal/Not-normal Yes = Normal LOS No = Longer or shorter LOS than normal	Length of stay: a) Admission & discharge date Confounders: b) Complications during birth and hospital stay Inclusion / exclusion criteria: c) Discharged home	Length of stay: a) Admission & discharge date Confounders: b) ICD codes + CHOP codes + DRG codes [mother / newborn] Inclusion / exclusion criteria: c) Place of discharge	a-c) administrative patient data

Table 3: Variables to be extracted

Variable	Target patient group	Calculation and Interpretation	Measurement intervals	Source of extraction
Main diagnosis & secondary diagnoses (ICD-10 GM)	Mother Newborn	NA	Once per hospital stay (case)	Administrative patient data
Main procedure & secondary procedures (CHOP)	Mother Newborn	NA	Once per hospital stay (case)	Administration patient data
DRG	Mother Newborn	NA	Once per hospital stay (case)	Administration patient data

Variable	Target patient group	Calculation and Interpretation	Measurement intervals	Source of extraction
Admission date Discharge date	Mother Newborn	NA	Once per hospital stay (case)	Administration patient data
Discharge place	Mother Newborn	NA	Once per hospital stay (case)	Administration patient data
Birth date	Mother Newborn	Mother: Age in years Newborn: Age in days	Mother: Once per hospital stay (case) Newborn: Every day after birth	Administration patient data
Birth weight	Newborn	NA	Once per hospital stay (case)	Administration patient data
Nationality	Mother	NA	Once per hospital stay (case)	Administration patient data
Medication	Mother	Medications of interest: - Nalbuphine - Nitrous oxide - Syntocinon	Documented by time point of administration	EHR (Meona)
Newborn feeding	Newborn	Feeding of interest: - Supplementary feeding within the last 24h before discharge	Documented by time point of administration	EHR (Meona)
Newborn monitoring data	Newborn	Monitoring data of interest: - Temperature - Glucose - Bilirubin	Documented by time point of measurement	EHR (Meona)

Variable	Target patient group	Calculation and Interpretation	Measurement intervals	Source of extraction
Exact pregnancy week	Mother (relevant for newborn)	Pregnancy week in week and days.	Documented for each day of hospital stay until birth.	EHR (Meona)
Parity (number of times given birth)	Mother	NA	Once per hospital stay (case)	EHR (Meona)
Blood loss	Mother	NA	Once per hospital stay (case)	EHR (Meona)

9. Application for an exemption according to Art. 34 HRA.

The general consent is implemented since 2016 in Basel. In 2018 only for 37% of all patients who came to the USB for treatment, a general consent could be found in the clinic information system. In the majority (85%) of them agreed to the use of their data for research (intranet and internal documents). This shows that the reason for the few general consents is not due to a lack of willingness on the part of the patients, but rather because the clinic staff ask little about it.

Ad Art 34 lit.a.: Women that plan to give birth in the USB receive the general consent form sent home some weeks before their due date. They are able to read this document, sign it and send it back to the USB. Given the unexpected and extraordinary nature of childbirth, the research consent process is often not prioritized in the hospital's administration or during birth and the postpartum stay. This includes obtaining consent from patients to use their routinely collected health-related data for research purposes. Very often the patients themselves cannot provide any feedback due to the clinical situation. It seems ethical not acceptable to ask the relatives in this exceptional situation about the general consent. It seems disproportionate to request the missing consent from the patients themselves or through the relatives. Patient with an explicit denial to the general consent will be excluded. Due to the large number of patients obtaining consent from each patient would be impractical or impossible.

Ad Art 34 lit.c: The benefit of this research seems promising. The expected results would help to better understand whether staffing is a driver and would provide guidance to improve patient care in the long run. The risk to individual patients from the use of routinely collected data seems low. Especially the approach to analyse healthy newborns and what they need to remain healthy is not studied often. With this approach no additional data needs to be collected on newborn health and this understudied group can profit from the results. Furthermore, in times where everywhere staff is reduced, this study showing the effect of staffing is expected to be highly relevant for staffing decisions in hospitals.

10. Confirmation that there is no documented refusal:

The project leader confirms that no health-related personal data and no biological material will be used if there is a written or documented verbal refusal from the person concerned.

11. Which group of persons is authorized to release the biological material and the health-related personal data?

NG: Niklaus Gygli (Nurse data scientist USB, MScN, RN)

12. Who takes responsibility for the reception of this data/biological material?

Prof. Dr. Michael Simon, PhD, RN (Associate Professor at the University of Basel in Switzerland (Institute of Nursing Science (INS)), Faculty of Medicine)

13. Which group of persons should be authorized to access the health-related personal data within the scope of this research project?

The uncoded data will be only accessible to Niklaus Gygli, who is not part of the research team. Niklaus Gygli will replace patient and case identifiers with Study-IDs and will keep the code list in a password protected directory.

Coded data will be accessible only to:

- MS: Prof. Dr. Michael Simon, (Associate Professor at the University of Basel, Institute of Nursing Science (INS)), Faculty of Medicine)
- LE: Luisa Eggenschwiler (RM, PhD cand, first author of study, University of Basel, Institute of Nursing Science (INS)), Faculty of Medicine)

- PW: Pascale Waldispühl (RN, MScN cand, the University of Basel, Institute of Nursing Science (INS)), Faculty of Medicine)
- LK: Laura Krattiger (RM, MScN cand, the University of Basel, Institute of Nursing Science (INS)), Faculty of Medicine)

14. Who is responsible for the protection of the data that have been released?

Prof. Dr. Michael Simon, PhD, RN (Associate Professor at the University of Basel in Switzerland (Institute of Nursing Science (INS)), Faculty of Medicine)

15. Reporting obligations

The ethics committee must be notified of any change of project leader in advance and of any changes to the information given in the authorisation.

The completion or discontinuation of the research project must be reported to the ethics committee within 90 days.

16. Data protection

Uncoded data, coding and storage of the key

After the variables are extracted from the CDW and pseudonymised by NG the linking process will be done by LE. The key lists will be saved at the USB and be kept by a trusted employee of the hospital (NG), which will be external to the study team. Thus, the identifiers will never leave the hospital. The key lists will be protected by a password that only the trusted employee knows and will be stored at servers of the USB. The identifiers are the combination of a word and a 5-digit random number. The identifiers in the mapping lists are:

- Patient identifiers will receive the word "patient", e.g., patient48213
- Case identifiers will receive the word "case", e.g., case14296

After the pseudonymisation all patient and case identifiers are deleted before the linkage process is initiated. Especially when working with routine data, which is not collected for study purposes, the extraction of data is not always straight forward. To ensure data quality, validity checks are done. When inconsistencies occur, this is the only option to check whether an error occurred during linkage or during data extraction from the EHR. This is why the data will not be anonymized but pseudonymised. This will allow to respond to potential errors, the key list will allow to review, where the error might have occurred.

The variables from different data sources (administrative patient data, EHR-data) will be linked using the pseudonymised case and patient identifiers. During this process, the date of birth for mothers is used to calculate the age in years and then deleted from the data. The date of birth for newborns is kept, as some variables, like bilirubin levels are dependent on the age in days of the newborn. The process is oriented to the methodology of the SPHN. No data will be kept on local computer (to increase security) and all raw data and the key list will be deleted at the end of the project.

Only people who are involved in the analyses process will have access to the deidentified data. The coded data will be stored on servers of the USB. The access is restricted to the research team (LE, MS, PW, LK) and only accessible through Virtual Private Network (VPN) and the USB account and is password protected. To avoid data loss regular backups are conducted by the USB. The routine data will be used conscientiously by a selected team of researchers (main analysis by LE, secondary analysis by PW) and the research team will consider and meet the highest ethical standards.

As the clinical routine data, which is used for this project, is already entered into a clinical application/database, we will not set up another database for data collection. The accessibility of the data for analysis will be granted by the CDW, which contains copies of all clinical data that are entered into the clinical applications of the hospital.

17. Information on the storage of data and samples

Raw data is stored in the CDW only. Extracted data, available in electronic format (csv) is only accessible by NG. The pseudonymised data (csv) will be kept on USB servers. The access is password protected only accessible by the study team. The access requires credentials from the USB and the directory is only accessible to the research team.

18. Retention period

The deidentified data will be archived and kept for 10 years at servers of the USB. The raw data and key list will be destroyed at the end of the study.

19. Ethical and regulatory requirements

Risk-benefit assessment:

A potential risk is the violation of confidentiality due to loss / disclosure of identifying personal data. The outlined data protection procedures including coding of data, restricted access to a small number of researchers and technical means minimizing the risks from the use of the data.

Due to the further use of health-related personal data and the retrospective design, we reduced the research burden for the target population to an absolute minimum. Especially the start of a new life and the moment of becoming parents is life changing. Therefore, it is of high relevance to investigate, to what extent staffing does impact that and what can be done to improve this experience.

The potential benefits we expect to gain from this project are greater than potential harm from the data use.

This project complies with the regulatory requirements of the HRA and the HRO. The prerequisite for carrying out the research project is the approval of the competent ethics committee.

20. Results / transparency / publication

The definition and measurement of staffing-sensitive salutogenic outcome will provide a first description of the prevalence of salutogenic outcomes in a university hospital of Switzerland. This will deliver first insights in understanding the current status of salutogenic outcomes in the maternity setting and their measurement via routine data. A better comprehension of salutogenic outcomes could show their potential of being quality indicators. As those outcomes are measurable in hospitals as well as in birth centres, those yield the potential to finally compare the service provision of the two different settings. The MaNtiS project will further provide first evidence about the effects of staffing on salutogenic outcomes for birth giving parents and newborns. Findings will offer clinical practice a perspective how to potentially address upcoming staffing shortages.

Throughout the project we discuss content, descriptive data and results with the local experts at the USB in bi-monthly meetings. We have met the president of the Swiss Midwifery Association

and she will be involved in the dissemination of the results. The dissemination is planned via various ways. Three peer-reviewed articles are planned in the journals BMC pregnancy and childbirth, and Midwifery. Furthermore, two peer-reviewed articles are planned, which are written by supervised master students. For German-speaking Europe, also non-peer reviewed articles are planned in the journal of the Swiss Midwifery Association (Obstetrica) and in the German journal for midwives (Hebamme). Oral presentations and posters will be presented at the International Conference of the German Society of Midwifery Science, the Swiss Midwifery Conference and the International Society for Clinical Biostatistics Annual Conference. A podcast from the Swiss Midwifery Association (Herztöne) is already recorded to inform the broader public about the project. All publications will be advertised and made accessible on the public MaNtiS project website (<https://mantis.nursing.unibas.ch/>) and through social media like LinkedIn. Furthermore, the results will be of interest for Swiss Universities of Applied Sciences entailing a midwifery graduate curriculum.

21. Funding / Data sharing / Declaration of interest

The PhD project is funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and the involved authors do not have any conflicts of interest. The SNSF requests all publications to be open access, which will be followed. All dissemination activities will only show aggregated data without any possibility to identify individuals.

Some journals also require an open science approach, which includes sharing of analysis code and data. Data will be shared upon request and if this does not comply with the publication routines of the journals, highly aggregated data will be made available (27).

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Präsident
Prof. Christoph Beglinger
Vizepräsident
Dr. Marco Schärer

Prof Dr Michael Simon
University of Basel
Bernoullistrasse 28
4056 Basel

Basel, 15.02.2024/JS

Verfügung der Ethikkommission Nordwest- und Zentralschweiz (EKNZ)

Project-ID	2024-00300
Projekttitle	Maternal and Neonatal outcomes in Association with midwifery Staffing - a causal inference framework
Master-/Doktorarbeit von	Eggenschwiler, Luisa
Projektleitung	Prof Dr Michael Simon
Sponsor	Prof Dr Michael Simon
Zentren	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Prof Dr Michael Simon, University of Basel, Basel

Entscheid

- Die Bewilligung wird erteilt
Diese Bewilligung gilt für die angekündigte Dauer der Studie, höchstens jedoch für 5 Jahre ab Datum dieser Verfügung.
- Die Bewilligung wird mit Auflagen erteilt
Diese Bewilligung gilt für die angekündigte Dauer der Studie, höchstens jedoch für 5 Jahre ab Datum dieser Verfügung.
- Die Bewilligung kann noch nicht erteilt werden
- Die Bewilligung wird nicht erteilt
- Auf das Gesuch wird nicht eingetreten

Anmerkungen / Auflagen / Bedingungen / Begründung

Keine.

Klassifizierung

- Forschungsprojekt gemäss HFV Kategorie: --
 - Forschung mit Personen
 - Weiterverwendung des biologischen Materials oder der gesundheitsbezogenen Personendaten
 - mit Verstorbenen
 - mit Embryonen / Föten
 - mit ionisierender Strahlung

Das Forschungsprojekt ist eine Weiterverwendung biologischen Materials und
Geschäftsführerin Irene Oberli | Tellplatz 11 | 4053 Basel | Tel 061 268 13 50 | eknz@bs.ch | www.eknz.ch

gesundheitsbezogener Personendaten bei fehlender Einwilligung (Art. 34 HFG, Art. 37-40 HFV)

a. Zweck der Weiterverwendung:

This research project aims to investigate the causal effect of midwifery staffing levels on maternal and neonatal salutogenic outcomes. There are five different outcomes that are targeted. 1) Physiological vaginal birth, 2) Labour pain, 3) Exclusive breastfeeding at hospital discharge, 4) Healthy newborn, 5) Length of stay. The effect of staffing will be evaluated on each of the outcomes separately.

b. Bezeichnung des biologischen Materials/der gesundheitsbezogenen Personendaten:

There will be different data sets that will be used. 1) Administrative patient data (ICD codes, CHOP codes, DRGs, age, length of stay). 2) Clinical patient data from the electronic health record (medication, newborn feeding, newborn temperature, newborn glucose levels and newborn bilirubin levels). The vast majority of data that will be used are available from administrative patient data which is collected for the federal office of statistics. The time frame of analyses is from 2019 to the end of 2022.

c. Personen, die berechtigt sind biologisches Material und gesundheitsbezogenen Personendaten weiterzugeben:

The uncoded data will be only accessible to Niklaus Gygli. Niklaus Gygli will replace patient and case identifiers with Study-IDs and will keep the code list in a password protected directory. Coded data will be accessible only to the core team.

d. Personen, die berechtigt sind biologisches Material und gesundheitsbezogene Personendaten entgegenzunehmen:

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Entscheidverfahren

- ordentliches Verfahren vereinfachtes Verfahren (AG34) Präsidialverfahren

Am Entscheid beteiligte Kommissionsmitglieder siehe Anhang.

Die Ethikkommission bestätigt, dass sie nach ICH-GCP arbeitet.

Gebühren

Betrag: CHF 1000.-- **Tarifcode:** 2.1

Gemäss der geltenden Gebührenordnung von swissethics.

Rechtsmittelbelehrung

Gegen diesen Entscheid kann an den Regierungsrat des Kantons Basel-Stadt (Rathaus, Marktplatz 9, 4051 Basel) rekuriert werden. Der Rekurs ist innert 10 Tagen seit Eröffnung des Entscheides bei der Rekursinstanz anzumelden; innert 30 Tagen, vom gleichen Zeitpunkt angerechnet, ist die Rekursbegründung einzureichen, welche die Anträge und deren Begründung mit Angabe der Beweismittel zu enthalten hat. Bei völliger oder teilweiser Abweisung des Rekurses können die Kosten der Rekurrentin respektive dem Rekurrenten ganz oder teilweise auferlegt werden.

Kopie an

- BAG
 Andere Luisa Eggenschwiler, luisa.eggenschwiler@unibas.ch

i.v. m. j. p. n. e. l.

Prof. Dr. med. Christoph Beglinger
Präsident

- Anhang:**
- Pflichten des Sponsors/der Prüfperson oder der Projektleitung
 - Mögliche Entscheide und ihre Bedeutung
 - Eingereichte Dokumente
 - Am Entscheid beteiligte Kommissionsmitglieder

Anhang

Pflichten des Sponsors/der Projektleitung

Einreichung Dokumente: revidierte Dokumente und neue Dokumente zur Studie/zum Projekt sollen ausschliesslich über das Web-Portal [BASEC](#) eingereicht werden, auf der entsprechenden Formularseite des betreffenden Gesuches. Obsolete Dokumente sind dabei zu entfernen und Datums- und Versionsangaben entsprechend zu ergänzen. Die erfolgten Änderungen müssen im Korrekturmodus abgefasst werden und zusätzlich als ‚clean‘-Version eingereicht werden. Die Studieninformationen und -einwilligungen, das Protokoll und die Amendments müssen in durchsuchbaren PDF-Dateien eingereicht werden, insbesondere müssen gescannte Dokumente eine Texterkennung durchlaufen haben (OCR). Das unterschriebene und datierte Begleitschreiben muss die Antworten auf eventuell von der EK gestellte Fragen enthalten. Revidierte Dokumente sind auch den weiteren Zulassungsbehörden zuzustellen, sofern diese involviert sind.

Anmerkung: Die zuständige Ethikkommission überprüft im Rahmen des Bewilligungsverfahrens Aufklärungsbogen und Einwilligungserklärung in einer der Amtssprachen Deutsch, Französisch oder Italienisch. Aufklärungsbogen und Einwilligungserklärung in einer anderen Sprache werden von der Ethikkommission lediglich zur Kenntnis genommen. Für die korrekte Übersetzung ist der Sponsor oder die Projektleitung verantwortlich.

Meldepflichten: Die rechtlich bindenden Melde- resp. Bewilligungspflichten an die Ethikkommission für wesentliche Änderungen, einen vorzeitigen Studienabbruch, unerwünschte Ereignisse u.a. sind einzuhalten ([Verordnungen des Bundes](#)). Der Abschlussbericht ist spätestens ein Jahr nach Studienende der Ethikkommission einzureichen.

Registrierungspflicht: Der Sponsor muss – falls es sich um einen klinischen Versuch handelt – diesen in einem [WHO-Primärregister](#) oder im Register der Nationalen Medizinbibliothek der USA ([clinicaltrials.gov](#)) erfassen und anschliessend diese Nummer im BASEC-Portal eingeben. Die Übertragung der erforderlichen Daten in das Swiss National Clinical Trials Portal ([SNCTP](#)) kann nach Bewilligung der Ethikkommission und Zustimmung des Gesuchstellers automatisch erfolgen. Die Informationen über den klinischen Versuch sind in beiden Registern öffentlich zugänglich. Zusätzlich veröffentlicht swissethics wenige Informationen wie Titel, Projekttyp oder Leit-Ethikkommission aller durch die kantonalen Ethikkommissionen bewilligten Gesuche auf [swissethics.ch](#) (ausser Phase-I-Studien).

Mögliche Entscheide und ihre Bedeutung

Die Bewilligung wird erteilt: Das Vorhaben kann gemäss bewilligtem Forschungsplan und im Rahmen der anwendbaren rechtlichen Bestimmungen durchgeführt werden. Weitere Bewilligungspflichten (Swissmedic/BAG) sind zu beachten

Die Bewilligung wird mit Auflagen erteilt: Das Vorhaben kann gemäss bewilligtem Forschungsplan gestartet werden und im Rahmen der anwendbaren rechtlichen Bestimmungen durchgeführt werden. Die Auflagen sind zu erfüllen und die Gesuchsunterlagen innert 30 Tagen entsprechend anzupassen. Die revidierten Dokumente werden nach Einreichung im Präsidialverfahren geprüft. Weitere Bewilligungspflichten (Swissmedic/BAG) sind zu beachten

Die Bewilligung kann noch nicht erteilt werden: Das Vorhaben kann noch nicht gestartet werden. Die nachfolgenden Bedingungen sind zu erfüllen bzw. die Fragen zu beantworten und die revidierten Dokumente erneut bei der Ethikkommission einzureichen. Die Ethikkommission überprüft die revidierten Dokumente und erteilt die Bewilligung, wenn die Bedingungen erfüllt bzw. die Fragen zufriedenstellend beantwortet sind.

Die Bewilligung wird nicht erteilt: Das Vorhaben kann in der vorliegenden Form nicht durchgeführt werden. Eine Neueinreichung ist möglich.

Auf das Gesuch wird nicht eingetreten: Begründung siehe vorne, z.B. nicht zuständig oder nicht bewilligungspflichtig.

Eingereichte Dokumente für das Hauptzentrum

Prof Dr Michael Simon, University of Basel, Basel		
Dokument	Dok.Datum	Version
1. Cover Letter		
begleitschreiben-mantis-2024-02-13.pdf	13/02/2024	
3. Participant information sheet and informed consent (ICF)		
forschungskonsent-info-d-v3-1-20210927.pdf	27/09/2021	3.1
forschungskonsent-efexample-d-v3-1-20210927.pdf	27/09/2021	3.1
4. Study plan (protocol), signed and dated		
mantis-outcomes-ethikantrag-2024-02-13.pdf	13/02/2024	1
6. Investigator's CV, dated		
michaelsimoncv-01022024.pdf	01/02/2024	
14. Information on secure handling of biological material and personal data, and in particular on the storage thereof		
see doc/cat: 4, page/ref: 15		
30. Proof of secure and correct coding		
see doc/cat: 4, page/ref: 15		
39. Miscellaneous / Varia		
template-use-case-evaluation-and-risk-assessment-v1-0-le-2024-02-13.xlsx	13/02/2024	1

Am Entscheid beteiligte Kommissionsmitglieder

	Name, Vorname	Berufliche Stellung / Titel	m	f	am Beschluss beteiligt	
					ja	nein
Vorsitz	Prof. Ch. Beglinger	Präsident	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Dr. R. Hauswirth	FMH Allgemeine Medizin, Leibstadt	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Dr. HR. Stoll	Pflegeexperte MSc / ehem. Stationsleiter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>